

EMPOWERING RURAL COMMUNITIES REVITALIZING TRADITIONAL CLAY POTTERY INDUSTRY IN ISHIAGU LGA, EBONYI STATE NIGERIA.

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17962813>

Abstract: This study aims to revitalize the traditional clay pottery industry in Ishiagu, Ebonyi state, Nigeria empowering rural communities through economic growth, cultural preservation and community engagement. Leveraging local resources and expertise, enhances artisan's livelihoods, promotes cultural heritage and contributes to sustainable development. A mixed methods approach engaged 200 stakeholders in Ishiagu LGA traditional clay pottery industry. Data collection utilized structured questionnaires analysed using a five (5) likert scale (acceptance criterion: 3.0). Hypothesis testing employed T-test and ANOVA at alpha level of 0.05. The Study identified key challenges facing traditional clay pottery revitalization in Ishiagu LGA: social, geopolitical, economic, administrative, staffing and legal constraints. It is recommended that clay pottery training center should be established; facilitate market research, access, and promotion. Collaborate with government agencies for infrastructure, funding and policy support, target women artisans for training and economic empowerment. Conclusively, revitalizing traditional clay pottery in Ishiagu LGA, Ebonyi State, Nigeria, offers a unique opportunity for empowering rural communities by leveraging local resources, expertise and cultural heritage. This initiative enhances artisan skills and income, preserve cultural heritage, fosters community engagement, and promote sustainable development and environmental conservation

Keyword: Empowering, Rural Communities, Traditional Clay, Pottery, Industry, Ishiagu LGA, Ebonyi State, Nigeria.

Introduction

Ishiagu, a rural community in Ebonyi state, Nigeria, is home to a rich cultural heritage and traditional craftsmanship, particularly in clay pottery. For generations, local potters have honed their skills, producing beautiful and functional pieces that are an integral part of the community's identity. However, the traditional clay pottery industry in Ishiagu faces numerous challenges, including declining demand, limited market access, and inadequate support infrastructure Adeniyi (2017) The significance of revitalizing this industry extends beyond preserving cultural heritage; it also holds potential for economic empowerment and sustainable development. By leveraging the abundant clay resources in the region and promoting innovative production techniques, the traditional clay pottery

industry can become a viable source of income for rural communities [Chukwu 2017, Umar 2017, Umar,2020 and Umar et 2017]

The study aims to explore the opportunities and challenges associated with revitalizing the traditional clay pottery industry in Ishiagu, Ebonyi State Nigeria. By examining the current state of the industry, identifying areas for improvement, and developing strategies for growth, this research seeks to contribute to the empowerment of rural communities and the preservation of cultural heritage

Objectives

Enhance artisanal skills and productivity

Increase market access and economic opportunities

Preserve cultural heritage and traditional knowledge

Foster community engagement and participation

Promote sustainable development and environmental conservation

During the pre-colonial period Ishiagu like other parts of has a rich cultural heritage dating back to the pre-colonial era. The area was inhabited by various ethnic groups, including the Igbo and Ezza people. These communities lived in small villages, engaging in subsistence farming, hunting and craftsmanship. Between 1900-1960 Ishiagu was part of Abakaliki Division, under the Ogoja province. The British colonial administration introduced western education, Christianity and modern infrastructure. The area remained relatively peaceful, with minimal resistance to colonial rule. Between 1960-1996 after Nigeria gained independence in 1960 Ishiagu became part of the eastern region, during the Nigeria civil war 1967-1970, Ishiagu was affected with many residents displaced or forced to flee. Immediately Ebonyi state was created in 1996. Ishiagu was one of the 13 local government areas. This development brought new opportunities for growth and development. Today Ishiagu LGA is a thriving agricultural hub, with major crops including rice, yams, and cassava. The area is also known for its rich clay deposits, supporting a thriving pottery industry. UNESCO (2018)

Notable landmarks and institutions in Ishiagu include Ishiagu clay pottery industry, Ishiagu Rice mill, Ebonyi state university Ishiagu campus, etc. in term of traditional rulers Ishiagu has a rich traditional leadership structure, with the following notable rulers eg Ezeogo Ishiagu (Paramount Ruler), Izzi clan council of Elders.

One of the economic activities in Ishiagu includes the following Agriculture (Rice, Yams. Cassava), Pottery, Artisanal mining (Clay, sand) and trading but the challenges faced in Ishiagu are infrastructure development, poverty reduction, education, healthcare access and environmental degradation. UNESCO (2018)

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Cultural Economy Theory

Cultural Economy Theory as proposed by Scott (2020) emphasizes the significance of cultural industries in driving local economic development. This theoretical framework recognizes the cultural sector as a vital component of the economy contributing to economic growth, job creation and urban regeneration the cultural sector as a vital drive of economic growth, urban development and social change

Scott's Cultural Economy Theory integrates concepts from

Marxist Economics. Emphasizing the role of cultural labor in value creation

Institutional Economics: Highlighting the importance of local institutions and governance

Geography: Examining the spatial dimension of cultural production and consumption Scott(2020)

Critiques and limitation

- a. Overemphasis on urban areas neglecting rural cultural economies
- b. Lack of attention to digital cultural economies. Overlooking online cultural production and consumption
- c. Insufficient consideration of cultural industry workforce conditions ignoring labor exploitation and precarity.

Conclusively the cultural Economy Theory provides a valuable framework for understanding the complex relationship between cultural, economy and spatiality. By recognizing the significance of cultural industries, policy makers and practitioners can harness their potential to drive economic growth, urban development, and social change FAD (2022)

3.0 History of Ishiagu

Ishiagu is a large clan community of seventeen villages varying in size in terms of land and population. It is one of the largest autonomous communities in Ivo Local Government Area. It is located on the plains of the south-eastern savannah belt in Nigeria.

In the case of the seventeen village groups that constitute Ishiagu clan community, most of the people of the seventeen villages identify themselves as belonging to a common ancestral descent, even though evidence abounds that the movements to, and the settlement in Ishiagu land, were piece-meal, uncoordinated, and occurred at different periods of time. It is difficult to imagine that the original eleven villages were of the same ancestry, in terms of being the offspring of members of one family.

The traditional method of sharing common community interests and things along the customary line suggests that the arrival and settlement of the early ancestors of each village to their present site differ greatly from the others. This traditional group-sharing method was symbolic of the differences in their periods of arrival. Each village community has its own traditional history of arrival and settlement. Even in one village there might exist several traditional histories of arrivals and settlements of the ancestors coming from quite different communities outside Ishiagu land. Chukwu (2017)

Some schools of thought hold the view that the purported dates of arrivals of the ancestors were not really arrival as imagined, but the community sharing technique was meant to reflect the period when each village came to join the other village groups. Through the passage of time it appeared that the founding fathers of Ishiagu community started to refer to the people of the eleven villages as the children or descendants of Echelle. The name Echelle started to be the second bond of unity after the acquired name of Ishiagu being applied to the land. Chukwu (2017)

The belief that Ishiagu people were the children of Echelle might have been derived from the need to provide a strong sense of unity, since there existed a central belief in Echelle as mythical, legendary or real founder of Ishiagu land. When one talks of a community one has in mind a number of people associating together on account of residence in the same locality, who are bound together by the same

laws, norms, belief systems and values. The terms are then applied to a group of people with a common territory and common interests and objectives. It may be necessary to distinguish a village community from a clan community.

A village community can be described as a cluster of people living within a continuous, somewhat small area, and who share a common way of life. A village community is usually a local territory group. On the other hand a clan community is a larger territorial group where people who live in the community can come from various village communities, but all are united in the belief that they have a common ancestral descent, and have certain common links such as religion, economy and tradition. Each village community may be made up of wards and kindred groups.

With this classification in mind, it can be asserted that Ishiagu clan community is made of seventeen village communities, each varying in size and population as well as the number of wards and kindred groups.

There are several smaller and larger village communities within Ishiagu clan community. There are certain unifying factors that tend to bind the seventeen village communities together to form a cohesive clan community. These will include the following:

All the inhabitants, except those who arrived at the scene late, and those who live close to the borders, speak the same dialect of Igbo language.

Religious belief and practices have always tended to unite people together. The entire people of the various village communities had tended to worship the same deities in ancient times, and Christianity has also brought all together in the modern time. It might be correct to say that religion not only provides social unity, but also a sense of meaning to life, and explanation to the mysteries of the world to those who share the same faith, and also promotes a sense of belonging among its members. The common belief that most of the villages had a common origin makes the unity of the clan people of Ishiagu much stronger. Chukwu (2017)

The influence of the Eke market as a unifying factor cannot be over emphasized. The choice of the market square to serve the socio-economic needs of the clan community had been a masterpiece, since the centrality of its location made it possible and easy for the people from the various village communities to meet there for purposes of exchange, social interaction and entertainment purposes. Cultural belief systems, values and practices are shared by all the members of village communities. There were common beliefs in the cycle of life under the watchful eyes of the ancestors, the existence of the land god, (ajali), the yam gods (aho, and njoku), and these factors tend to exert a strong unifying influence on the people. The regulation of the agricultural activities of the people from one season to another, in order to complete the cycle of year, provides a very strong force to unite the people as belonging to one clan. World Bank (2020)

These factors demonstrate that Ishiagu people have since been occupying a definite geographical area known and called Ishiagu, and that they had since been constituted as a self-governing social unit long before the colonial era. They have developed to a high degree some common values and have been experiencing a sense of belonging to one another, but that each village had always tended to maintain

its own separate identity and limited autonomy in certain respects. This is why it might be true to say that Ishiagu clan community is made up of seventeen semi-autonomous village communities.

Figure 1 show the map of Ishiagu in Ebonyi state and its environs. Umar (2020)

Map showing Ishiagu LGA and its environs

Source: Researcher's Field Survey (2025).

Picture1 showing the scenes from Ishiagu Community, Ebonyi State, Nigeria: A Glimpse into the timeless Tradition of clay pottery Making.

Source: Researcher's Field Survey (2025).

Source: Researcher's Field Survey (2025).

4.0 Research Methodology

The study employed a survey research design, incorporating both qualitative and quantitative data. Collection methods. Qualitative data were gathered through oral interviews and non-participant observation, while quantitative data were collected using structured questionnaires and secondary sources such as books and journal articles. The oral interview targeted local traditional clay pottery makers, artisan and other relevant stakeholders. The interviews were conducted based on questions drawn from prepared interview guide and recorded manually. Non-participant observation data were derived using an observation schedule and photographic materials during several visits to Ishiagu. Due to the logistical constraints, the study focused on local stakeholders and avoided interviewing visitors or travelers to the area, in order to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the observed data and inferences.

5.0 Research Finding

From the research finding based on the table below, it shows that the respondents mean score (range from 3.52 to 4.27) each dimension of social problem was above the criterion mean of 3.0 set for the research. The table also show that the respondents overall mean score for social problem constituted a problem for the revitalization of clay pottery making in Ishiagu LGA, especially the socioeconomic characteristics of clay pottery makers in Ishiagu LGA and how do these factor influence their participation in the industry and the traditional techniques and methods used in clay pottery making in Ishiagu LGA, and how can these be integrated with modern technologies to enhance productivity (with a mean of 4.27 and 4.17 respectively) the standard deviation show that the responses provided by the respondents did not vary so widely.

Table 1

S/N	Statement	X	SD
1	What are the socioeconomic characteristics of clay pottery makers in Ishiagu LGA and how do these factors influence their participation in the industry	4.27	1.03
2	What traditional techniques and methods are used in clay pottery making in Ishiagu LGA, and how can these be integrated with modern technologies to enhance productivity	4.17	.88
3	What are the current challenges facing the traditional clay pottery industry in Ishiagu?	3.60	.51
4	How can the traditional clay pottery industry in Ishiagu be revitalized through innovative technologies, marketing strategies and entrepreneurship development?	3.52	.48
5	What role can community-based initiatives, cooperative, and women's groups play in empowering rural communities to revitalize the traditional clay pottery industry?	3.81	.60
6	What policy interventions and support mechanisms are necessary to promote the growth and development of the traditional clay pottery industry in Ishiagu	3.58	.52

Key x=Mean SD= standard Deviation

Source: Source: Researcher's Field survey and Analysis 2025

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2025

How can the traditional clay pottery industry in Ishiagu be developed and empowered through community led initiatives and participatory decision-making processes

Table 2

Community- Led Initiatives

Initiative	Mean score	Standard Deviation
Training and capacity Building	4.20	0.80
Market Access and linkages	4.00	0.90
Financial support and credit	4.10	0.80
Infrastructure Development	3.90	0.90
Marketing and promotion	4.00	0.80

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2025

Table 3

Participatory Decision- Making Processes

Process	Mean score	Standard Deviation
Regular Meeting with Artisans	4.50	0.60
Inclusion Decision-Making	4.30	0.70
Transparency and Accountability	4.40	0.60
Community Engagement and participation	4.20	0.70

Empowerment of women and youth	4.10	0.70
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Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2025

Table 4

Development and Empowerment indicators

Indicators Mean score Standard Deviation

Indicators	Mean score	Standard Deviation
Increased income	4.25	0.75
Improved Product Quality	4.15	0.80
Enhanced Market Access	4.30	0.70
Strengthened Community Cohesion	4.20	0.75
Empowerment of women and youth	4.10	0.80

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2025

Interpretation

- Mean scores range from 1(low) to 5 (high)
- Standard deviation scores indicate the level of variation in responses
- Higher mean scores and lower standard deviation scores indicate greater importance, effectiveness, or consensus among respondents

The analysis of the mean scores and standard deviations reveals that community-led initiatives, particularly training and capacity building are crucial for the development of the traditional clay pottery industry in Ishiagu LGA. With a mean score of 4.20 and a standard deviation of 0.80 therefore training and capacity building emerge as the most critical initiatives, emphasizing the importance of community training and retention. This, in turn enables community members to train others in their areas, promoting the marketing and global recognition of their clay pottery products

Furthermore, the results indicate that participatory decision-making processes, especially regular meeting with artisans are vital for the industry's growth. The high means scores of 4.50 and low standard deviation of 0.60 underscore the significance of regular meetings in promoting the clay pottery industry.

In terms of development and empowerment indicators, enhanced market access stands out as a critical factor, with a mean score of 4.30 and a standard deviation of 0.70. This highlights the importance of market access in ensuring the economic empowerment of women and youth in the industry

6.0 RECOMMENDATION/CONCLUSION

- i. Establish Training and capacity Building programs; implement regular training sessions for artisans to enhance their skills and knowledge in traditional clay pottery production, marketing and entrepreneurship
- ii. Develop market Access and linkages. Create market linkages for artisans to access local, national and international markets, ensuring fair prices and sustainable livelihoods.

- iii. Provide financial support and credit facilities : Establish microfinance schemes or cooperative to provide artisans with access to credit, enabling them to invest in their businesses and improve productivity
- iv. Promote participatory decision making: foster regular meeting and workshops with artisans, community leaders, and stakeholders to ensure inclusive decision making and collective ownership of the industry's development
- v. Enhance infrastructure and technology: upgrade infrastructure, such as kilns, workshops, and storage facilities and introduce appropriate technologies to improve efficiency, quality and competitiveness
- vi. Empower women and youth. Implement targeted programs to empower women and youth in the industry providing them with training mentorship, and access to resources and markets.
- vii. Develop a marketing strategy: create a comprehensive marketing strategy to promote the traditional clay pottery industry in Ishiagu, both locally and internationally
- viii. Establish partnership and collaborations; foster partnerships with government agencies, NGOs, and private sector organizations to access resources, expertise and markets

CONCLUSION

Revitalizing the traditional clay pottery industry in Ishiagu, Ebonyi State, Nigeria requires a multi-faceted approach that addresses the complex challenges facing the industry. By implementing the recommended strategies, the industry can be empowered to combine significantly to the local economy, improve livelihoods, and preserve cultural heritage

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